

Science Teachers' Lived Experiences in Promoting STEM Career Interests among Rural High School Students in Masbate

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Abstract. This qualitative phenomenological study explored the lived experiences of Science Teachers in promoting Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) career interests among rural high school students in Masbate. Through semi-structured interviews with 8 Science Teachers from public secondary schools in the 2nd district of Masbate, this research aimed to understand the science teachers' lived experiences, the strategies, programs, initiatives, the challenges, and the impact of science teachers' efforts in promoting the STEM career interests among the students. The study utilized Colaizzi's phenomenological method for data analysis that resulted in formulation of four main themes and twelve subthemes. Experiential Learning and Real-World Relevance, Role Modeling and Career Exposure, Academic Preparedness Issues and Limited STEM Knowledge, and Building Confidence and Encouraging Curiosity. The findings revealed that hands-on activities, inquiry-based learning, and career exposure programs were essential to make the STEM careers attainable and relevant for students. The science teachers must provide more opportunities among the students to engage in experiments, problem-solving task, research activities, laboratory work, and community-based STEM projects. The science teachers' role as mentors and their personal experiences in STEM served as powerful motivators that shaped the students' confidence, aspirations, and career decisions. On the other hand, challenges such as lack of resources and opportunities, limited awareness and knowledge of diverse STEM careers, personal barriers and motivation, peer and family influences limit the full students' engagement in STEM. Science teachers mentioned the positive changes among the students' attitudes towards STEM careers, emphasizing the effectiveness of mentorship, reinforcement and support, and practical exposure. With all the results gathered it needs to enhance the hands-on and inquiry-based learning, increase STEM career awareness, provide adequate resources and opportunities, and strengthen the teachers mentorship.

Keywords: Career Promotion; Experiential Learning; Rural High School; Science Teachers; STEM Education

Introduction

In the Philippines Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics careers are globally recognized as an important factor in economic growth, innovation, and sustainable development. The STEM related careers contribute meaningfully to address the global challenges such as technological advancement, environmental sustainability, and economic competitiveness. The study revealed of Berry et al. (2022) and Rahman (2024) that the students' interest in Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics careers was molded and shaped with meaningful learning experiences that the student encounters such as hands-on activities and exposure to the real-world problems that emphasized the importance of science teachers in guiding and facilitating the students toward STEM opportunities.

The nation educational landscape, promotion of STEM education has been emphasized through curriculum reforms and national initiatives aimed at increasing student participation in STEM fields. Meanwhile, despite these efforts the studies shown that many Filipino students still have limited awareness of STEM career opportunities, and engagement in activities related to STEM that may varies widely across regions (Dacumos, 2023; Punzalan, 2022). Science teachers play a critical role in addressing this gap, as their

instructional practices and encouragement significantly influence students' interest and motivation toward STEM careers (Camilon, 2023; Lubrica et al., 2021).

Science, technology, Engineering, and Mathematics education in Masbate Province presents various challenges that may affect both teaching and learning process. In the rural high schools often experience shortages in instructional resources, laboratory facilities, technological access, and professional development opportunities for teachers (Goodpaster et al., 2012; Margot & Kettler, 2019). In the Philippine studies further emphasized that rural science teachers face additional burdens such as heavy workloads, curriculum misalignment, and limited access to STEM-related training that challenged effective STEM instruction and career promotion (Ferrell et al., 2024; Geverola et al., 2022; Tijap et al., 2022). These challenges limit students' exposure to STEM experiences and role models that affect the students career interest.

In rural high schools specifically in the 2nd district of Masbate the science teachers assume roles that extend beyond content delivery. This locale was chosen because its unique educational landscape that reflects a mix of urban and rural settings with varied access to STEM resources and the presence of schools with both high and low exposure to science and technology programs. The science teachers serve as guide and facilitators of inquiry-based learning, implementers of contextualized and project-based strategies, informal career advisers, and role models who influence students' perceptions of STEM fields. Philippine phenomenological studies (Ambroce & Daza, 2025; Bayot, 2024; Gevera, 2025; Rosas, 2019) show common patterns of resilience, adaptability, reflective practice, and pedagogical innovation among science teachers, particularly when faced with limited resources, curriculum misalignment, and contextual constraints. Through these lived experiences of science teachers integrate STEM career awareness into everyday instruction and motivate students to explore STEM-related opportunities.

The existing review related literatures and studies examines STEM teaching strategies, student motivation, and career guidance programs that most of the research emphasizes instructional outcomes or student perspectives using quantitative or descriptive approaches. Meanwhile, lack of phenomenological studies that center on science teachers' lived experiences as the primary viewpoints for understanding STEM career promotion particularly in rural high schools. Moreover, there are limited research studies that captures the teachers' own perspectives on how their efforts influence students' attitudes, interests, and career intentions toward STEM despite evidence that teacher encouragement and role modeling are critical factors in STEM persistence (Mao et al., 2021; Popa & Ciascai, 2017; Simons et al., 2025).

The 2nd district of Masbate a rural province that faced many of the structural and contextual challenges identified in rural STEM education literature. Understanding the lived experiences of science teachers in Masbate was significant for developing context-responsive strategies that strengthen STEM career promotion in rural high schools in the province. By examining science teachers' experiences, strategies, challenges, perceived influence on students, and proposed recommendations the present study provided localized and experience-based evidence that informed instructional practice, school-based initiatives, and policy decisions. Ultimately, this study contributed to science education literature and rural STEM advocacy by grounding STEM promotion efforts in the authentic experiences of science teachers in Masbate.

Research Questions

This study aimed to explore and describe the lived experiences of Science Teachers in promoting Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) career interests among rural high school students in Masbate. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the lived experiences of Science Teachers in promoting STEM career interests among rural high school students in Masbate?
2. What strategies, programs, and initiatives do Science Teachers use to promote students' interest, participation in STEM-related activities, and career orientation?
3. What are those challenges Science Teachers encounter in implementing STEM promotion initiatives within rural high schools?
4. How do Science Teachers view their efforts in influencing students' attitudes, interests, and career intentions?
5. What recommendations can be proposed by the researcher based on the results of the study?

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study primarily explored the lived experiences of Science Teachers in promoting Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) interests among rural high school students in Masbate. The scope of this study included Junior High School Science Teachers teaching science subjects in public rural high schools in the 2nd district of Masbate. This study centered on Science Teachers' first-hand narratives of engaging in STEM career promotion through classroom practices, mentoring, lesson integration

for career awareness, school-based STEM activities, and other initiatives that Science Teachers perceived as influential in shaping students' attitudes and career intentions. This study was limited to the rural high schools in the 2nd district of Masbate Province. Urban schools and private institutions are excluded from this study.

Literature Review

Lived Experiences of Science Teachers in Promoting STEM Career Interest

Based in the Philippine studies conducted about the lived experiences, narratives, insights, and perceptions of Science Teachers that emphasize the important role in shaping students' interest towards STEM career interest. Using a qualitative phenomenological approach, Rosas (2019) revealed that despite limited resources and content misalignment with teachers' specialization, science teachers employed adaptive strategies, reflective practices, and innovative teaching approaches to sustain students' engagement in science, which indirectly promotes interest in STEM related careers opportunities. Similar to the study of Bayot (2024) through in-depth interviews and Colaizzi's method the researcher documented science teachers' lived experiences during the COVID-19 pandemic and based on the findings it emphasized teachers' resilience, pedagogical flexibility, and strong sense of responsibility in maintaining students' interest in science areas even under modular approach and remote learning conditions that factors an essential in sustaining STEM motivation and promotion. Ambroce and Daza (2025) based on the findings of this study that the trials of teaching beyond the teachers specialization such as mastering contents and preparation struggles, the adaptive strategies, supportive communities, and growth beyond boundaries. These findings suggest that teacher preparedness and supports systems are important on how the Science Teachers influence students career mindsets and attitudes toward science or STEM. A study of Gevera (2025) revealed that the experiences of the teachers with inquiry-based strategies revealed real-world classroom challenges, adaptive teaching practices, and pedagogical reflections. It also includes the issues with strategy implementation, the reflection of teachers during practices, and classroom dynamics that the students engagement shape for science learning linked to STEM career interests. Simons et al (2025) stated that the Teachers' lived experiences of marginalization informed pedagogical commitments to inclusive STEM learning environments that they helped broaden students' perceptions of who belong to STEM. The study revealed advocacy as part of teaching identity that influencing how the teachers presented STEM careers and encouraged multiple pathways into STEM.

Strategies, Programs, and Initiatives to Promote STEM

The project-based learning in STEM context and showed the project-based learning helps make the STEM more tangible, promote engagement, and link to 21st century skills (Dacumos, 2023). However, according to Rahman (2024) discusses how modern pedagogical practices including the inquiry-based learning, robotics, programming, and computer-based scaffolding are being used globally to the STEM more interactive and engaging for the students. In the studies of Lopez, Morgan, Hutchings, & Davis (2022) conducted a systematic review that highlights the LSAMP (Louis Stokes Alliances for Minority Participation) as one of the initiatives because LSAMP provides mentoring, research opportunities, and pedagogical innovation but stresses sustainability and institutionalization for those practices. The review conducted of Berry et al. (2022) they categorize initiatives into the policy, pedagogy, influence & support, and promotion & engagement. Reform our institutional policies and ensure teaching methods are inclusive for every student through mentorship and peer network for actively engaging with future students before entering the college. The Department of Science and Technology-Science Education Institute started using the 21st Century Learning Environment Model (21st CLEM) to get the student interested in STEM. This model implement immersive technology such as robotics, 3D printing, Virtual and augmented reality, adoptive ICT tools to make science and math more interesting for students (DOST-SEI, 2024). According by Lubrica et al. (2021) also revealed that interactive science exhibits such as the hands-on science equipment in the Grades 7 to 10 can increase students' interest in the STEM careers. Based on the study in Davao emphasized that exposure to STEM contexts through school and community activities helps shaping students in STEM career aspiration, showing that supportive environment is important in maintaining students' interest in STEM related careers (Provendido et al., 2024)

Career Orientation and Guidance Approaches for Career Promotion

The study conducted by Punzalan (2022) a quantitative survey of 334 junior high students in the Philippines measuring the STEM subject interest and construct of FCP. The findings indicated that there is no significant gender differences in overall STEM interests or Future Career Perspectives (FCP) construct,

both males and females showed moderate interests in most STEM subjects. Correlation between FCP components were weak to moderate, with strong positive link between personal value and enjoyment of STEM learning. The descriptive-correlational documentary study across 60 public secondary schools in the division of Bohol the data from 1200 Grade 11-12 students, plus 60 guidance councilors and 60 homeroom advisers. Their findings indicated the implementation of career guidance varied in educational qualifications, job descriptions, years of experiences, lack of training, lack of resources, and time constraints that significantly affect delivery of career guidance activities. In this study found that career guidance activities as implemented did not show a direct correlation with students' actual career choices (Maestrado & Bucar, 2024). The study conducted by Ilagan (2021) showed that while high school guidance helped students choose academic decisions, their final decisions were strongly influenced by factors that includes the personal interests of the students, input from family, and financial considerations. The quantitative correlation conducted by Blotnick et al. (2018) their findings the interest in mathematics and science alone does not predict STEM career choices but the study proves that orientation seminars explaining specific job roles are more effective for recruitment than academic tutoring. The study conducted by Camilon (2023) stated that research highlights the students' career choices is STEM are strongly influenced by role models, access to meaningful learning experiences, and participation in co-curricular activities.

Student Attitudes, Interests, Motivation, and Intentions towards STEM

The reviewed studies collectively show that the students' attitudes, motivations, and career intentions toward the STEM are shaped by the combination of personal beliefs, the learning experiences, and the contextual influences. The across multiple quantitative studies about self-efficacy consistently emerges as the strongest predictor of the STEM performances and career choices with Mao et al. (2021) confirming its rise and Popa and Ciascai (2017) that demonstrated that the students feel confident for the subject of math and science are the one to pursue the STEM fields or careers. Gender patterns also appears as Mahoney (2010), Wang et al. (2023) and Sung et al. (2025) found that male students tend to show more positive STEM attitudes although these differences vary across subdomains such as technology and engineering. The learning environments play an important role among the students. Canning et al. (2024) emphasized that active learning can boost the internal motivation of the students. The study of Sahin and Waxman (2021) emphasized that the earliest STEM interest must remain constant up high school and particularly when it is supported by the high science self-efficacy. Different drivers for males such social support and females such media and environment (Wang et al. 2023). The peer support and parents with related STEM occupations encourage persistence despite a demanding curriculum (Perez et al., 2021). Contextualized interventions matter or solutions according to Sung et al. (2025) demonstrated that design-based strategies, the culturally familiar STEM activities aligned to their community are significantly can improve and enhance rural students attitudes that are strengthened by teachers' own positive value towards STEM. Together, these studies suggest that the enhancing STEM motivation requires addressing personal confidence, providing engaging learning experiences, and leveraging social and cultural supports.

Rural Education Context

The reviewed studies consistently point out that the rural students' persistence in STEM is shaped by the mix of the community strengths and the structural barriers. The qualitative findings from Jones and Emenike (2024) show that strong sense of community, mentoring, and the validation of rural identity are center to retaining rural students then highlighting the need for the university programs or courses that integrate the academic, social, and identity-based support systems. Cain et al. (2024) similarly found that although rural schools often lack of resources, the rural students possess unique forms of community capital that sustain their STEM aspirations. From the educators' perspective, Goodpaster et al. (2012) and Margot and Kettler (2019) revealed that the rural teachers value strong interpersonal relationships and the trust in their communities, up to now face persistent barriers such as the resource shortages, the limited professional development, the curriculum misalignment, and the geographic isolation all of which prevent effective STEM delivery. Students struggle in limited exposure, social, and geographical isolation, and difficulty transitioning to urban postsecondary settings, making mentorship and targeted institutional interventions or solution are significant for retention of the students in rural condition (Adam et al., 2024).

Challenges Encountered by Science Teachers

Descriptive phenomenology study emphasized that science seen as challenging subject that needs for content mastery, the teachers faced difficulties in distance learning modalities, teachers had to adopt new strategies for instruction and student engagement and interaction, challenges included limited digital tools and students readiness issues (Geverola et al., 2022). The study of Tijap et al. (2022) point out in the survey research with 464 Filipino science teachers that teachers reported needing upskilling them about digital

tools, online assessment trainings, and instructional designs. It also revealed that insufficient preparation for online platforms may contribute to the teacher stress and limited engagement towards students. Based on the Ferrell et al. (2024) literature discussion it emphasized that the rural teachers face limited training aligned to professional development, narrow pedagogy, and limited resources at school. Another findings from the study emphasized that the place-based learning can leverage local environments to enhance STEM learning among students and emphasizes the need for community integrations and adult involvements. The qualitative research study of Ismail et al. (2019) gathered from 15 science teachers highlights the multiple challenges in STEM empowerment and promotion that it includes the limited training and professional development towards STEM education, lack of facilities and resources to implement STEM activities, Inadequate budget allocation. However, the science teachers suggested collaboration with the universities, colleges, industry partners, and targeted STEM training as solution for the difficulties. The qualitative exploration emphasized lack of coherent understanding of integration STEM concepts leads to instructional uncertainty and teachers' beliefs about STEM often conflicted with educational system expectations and pressures (Aslam et al., 2023)

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a phenomenological research design. This design was appropriate for this study because it sought to capture the lived experiences of Science Teachers as they promote STEM career interests among rural high school students in the 2nd district of Masbate. According to Gill (2020), phenomenological research investigated the structure of the phenomenon and required the researcher to set aside prior assumptions to engage fully with participants' meaning-making. Therefore, this research design aligned with the research questions.

Sampling Design

This study utilized purposive sampling, selected science teachers who could provide rich and in-depth descriptions of their lived experiences in promoting STEM career interest among rural high school in Masbate. Purposive sampling was commonly used in qualitative study to explore the phenomena of the participants experiences (Palinkas et al., 2015). This sampling method was suited for this study. A sample of 8 Science Teachers was enough for in-depth qualitative exploration, with phenomenological research standards.

Research Locale

The participating schools in the rural municipalities of Masbate Province where the students faced challenges such as limited laboratory facilities, inadequate instructional materials, insufficient internet connectivity, and restricted access to STEM enrichment programs. These realities directly influenced the teaching and learning process and the implementation of STEM promotion initiatives. This study was conducted in the selected public rural secondary schools located within the 2nd district of Masbate, part of the Bicol Region, Philippines. The 2nd district of Masbate included the municipalities of Aroroy, Baleno, Balud, Mandaon, Milagros, and Mobo as shown in figure 1. These conditions made the Masbate Province a meaningful and relevant location for examining how Science Teachers promoted the STEM career interests among the rural high school students. The participating schools in the rural municipalities of Masbate Province where the students faced challenges such as limited laboratory facilities, inadequate instructional materials, insufficient internet connectivity, and restricted access to STEM enrichment programs. These realities directly influenced the teaching and learning process and the implementation of STEM promotion initiatives.

Research Participants

The participants of this study were Science teachers from selected public rural high schools in the 2nd district of Masbate Province. Specifically, these teachers were currently teaching in rural public secondary schools and had a minimum of five years of experience handling junior high school science subjects. Additionally, they possessed at least a master's degree or had earned Certificate of Academic Requirements (CAR) in their graduate studies. All participants willingly took part in the study and shared their professional experiences through interviews.

Research Instrument

The primary instrument of this study for data gathering was a semi-structured interview guide developed by researcher. The researcher named the instrument "Science Teachers' Lived Experiences (STLE)

Questionnaire". The interview guide included open-ended questions which aligned the research questions. The validity of the research instrument the interview guide undergo a thorough content validation process. The STLE questionnaire was then submitted to the adviser and 3 experts in science education prior to the data collection. They assessed the STLE Questionnaire in terms of the clarity, relevance, and alignment with the research questions. Their suggestions and recommendations were incorporated to the STLE Questionnaire for refinement of words and structures. This study ensured the reliability through the trustworthiness of the research process. Refinement was made accordingly for the improvement of the instrument and to ensure the credibility the member checking was employed wherein the participants were given the opportunity to verify the accuracy of the transcribed responses and the interpreted meanings based on their statements. The audio recording devices were used with participants' consent to accurately capture responses.

Data Gathering Procedure

The process of gathering the data for phenomenological qualitative research was conducted systematically to ensure the credibility of this study. The researcher will formally requested permission to conduct this study from the Schools Division Superintendent of the Department of Education Masbate Province Division since the participants were the Science Teachers of public high schools in the 2nd district of Masbate. Then, the researcher submitted copies of the approved letter to the respective School Principals of identified rural high schools. The researcher explained the purpose of this study to the School Principals and asked for their cooperation in facilitating access to the Science Teachers for their participation. After receiving approval, the researcher identified the potential participants based on the criteria. All participants were given an informed consent form that participation was voluntary, their responses were confidential, and the participants could withdraw their participation without any consequences. After all, the formal data collection began. The researcher scheduled the one-on-one interviews with each participant based on participants' convenient time and place, preferably within the school premises or via online platform. The interview lasted within 30–60 minutes depends on the response of participants using audio recording with consent. The semi-structures interview format allowed to probe deeper into participants' responses while ensuring focus in the research questions (DeJonckheere & Vaughn, 2019).

Results and Discussions

Lived Experiences of Science Teachers in Promoting STEM Career Interests

The science teachers played a central role in cultivating students' interests in STEM careers by translating curriculum content into meaningful and real-world learning experiences. Their teaching practices, classroom interactions to the students, and school initiatives and programs that provided insights on how to develop the awareness, confidence, and motivation of students toward STEM. The teachers' use of real-world examples, problem-solving, and career-relevant projects that influenced STEM career aspirations among the students (Lopez et al., 2022). The emerged themes from the lived experiences of science teachers in promoting STEM career interests in Masbate are classified as Experiential Learning and Real-World Relevance with subthemes the hands-on learning and practical exposure, and inquiry-based classroom approach.

Experiential Learning and Real-World Relevance

This main theme understands the overall lived experiences of Science Teachers in Masbate in using practical and meaningful learning experiences that promote interests among students in STEM careers. Through experiential learning the students are not only exposed to concepts however they are also given the opportunities to learned through hands-on activities, problem-solving tasks, and collaborative projects. This experiential learning strengthens the critical thinking and creativity among the students to actively participate in the learning process. This theme emphasized the role of hands-on, interactive learning activities in promoting the STEM career interest among the students in rural high school in Masbate. Rahman (2024) explained that inquiry-based learning and other modern pedagogical practices make STEM more interactive and engaging for students.

One of the participants mentioned that:

"In most cases during my daily classroom tasks, I regularly used Problem-Based strategy to ensure that students are able to connect my lessons to real life situations." (ST3)

The science teacher used the problem-based learning to connect the lessons to the real-life situation and they helped the students to apply the theoretical concepts to practical, real-world problems, promote critical thinking, and problem skills.

"Yearly, we conduct science fairs and research-based activities where activities are centered on engaging and encouraging students' skills to be shared, interest to show through visiting booths, and open understanding of science-worldview." (ST8)

They conducted the annual science fairs and research-based activities to engage the students because it encouraged students to share their skills, show their interests, and deepen their understanding about STEM. Through visiting booths the students gained hands-on learning experiences.

"After consistent exposure to hands-on experiments, I've seen students start to broaden their thinking. Some who once thought they couldn't succeed in science begin expressing interest in careers like engineering, computer science, research." (ST1)

They observed that after the exposure of students in hands-on experiment then the students began to think wider. By this, the shift in mindset that reflected the positive impact of practical and experience-based learning.

The experiential learning played an important role in promoting the interest among the students about STEM careers in rural secondary schools in Masbate through hands-on activities, problem-based activities, and collaborative projects that students were able to apply the theories to real experience. This main theme had 2 subthemes the hands-on learning and practical exposure and inquiry-based classroom approach.

Hands-on learning and Practical Exposure

This subtheme emphasized the Science Teacher participants' experiences in using the experiential learning such as hands-on activities and practical involvement that these exposures connected the lessons to real-life experiences and potential STEM careers. The hands-on approach allowed the students to engage more with the subject matter to analyze and explore deeply, as the students can see, touch, and manipulate the learning materials for better experience. The practical exposure agreed with Dacumos (2023) on project-based learning. The study highlighted that the interactive science exhibits and exposure to STEM contexts is important (Lubrica et al., 2021; Provendido et al., 2024). Lastly, Camilon (2023) on meaningful learning experiences and co-curricular participation.

One of the participants described as:

"When I have the topic on Layers of the soil Instead of relying on diagrams, I wanted them to see and touch what soil layers actually look like. We went outside the school grounds and collected soil samples from different spots. By just making most of what is already available. I rely heavily on low-cost, high-impact strategies. Simple classroom materials, everyday objects, and the students' own environment become learning tools." (ST1)

All the participants experienced the importance of hands-on and practical exposure in promoting STEM career interests among the students that involved the used of the senses for meaningful learning experiences.

"The use of hands-on or inquiry-based learning approach also allows to have meaningful experiential learning and this can have a big impact on them. When learners enjoy learning the science subject / lessons, they will likely pursue courses/career in line with STEM." (ST2)

Another participant shared their experiences about hands-on learning activities and connects it to the real context.

"One of my most meaningful experiences was engaging students in hands-on STEM activities that connected lessons to real-world situations." (ST4)

They emphasized that hands-on learning and real-world exposure can help to enhance the engagement among the students in the STEM, influence their career interests. Science teachers in rural secondary schools in Masbate and effectively use inquiry-based learning, practical activities, and career exposure to bridge the gap between theoretical lessons and real-world applications in helping students see the relevance of STEM careers.

The schools needed to provide more resources like laboratory equipment and materials, programs for career guidance, and to support for STEM education. Teacher training on innovative teaching methods, have partnerships with industry professionals were important to improve the career orientation and the students to provide real-world STEM experiences. Overcoming these challenges that can create a more open and engaging STEM learning environment in rural high schools.

Inquiry-based Classroom Approach

This subtheme reflected the Science Teacher participants' experiences in using the inquiry-based learning as their educational strategies to show the essence of questioning, exploring, and discovering the solution through investigation conducted by the students. This learning approach enhanced the students' curiosity and critical thinking as they explore the topic independently and collaboratively to formulate

questions and educational guess along the process. This subtheme agreed strongly with Rahman (2024), which emphasized that inquiry-based learning makes STEM more interactive and engaging, and with Gevera (2025), which found that inquiry-based strategies involve real-world classroom challenges and adaptive teaching practices that shape students' science engagement.

One of the participant said that:

"Inquiry-based learning- I let students experiment, test and observe rather than just listen." (ST1)

The participant shared that inquiry-based learning was helpful to unleash the potential among the students specifically engaging in experiment that they are allowed to observe and make conclusion.

Six (6) out of eight (8) participants claimed the following;

"inquiry-based learning, where students are guided to ask questions, design investigations, collect and analyze data, and draw evidence-based conclusions." (ST5)

The participants emphasized that asking questions and investigation project, and providing evidence was helpful in students' part to engage and embrace the importance of STEM.

"I also encourage them through hands-on investigations, simple research projects, and problem-solving tasks to help them experience the excitement of discovery." (ST7)

The science teacher emphasized the essence of active participation and hands-on engagement in the learning process of student. Rather than being passive recipients of knowledge the students are encouraged to actively engage by experimenting, testing hypotheses, and observing the outcomes.

Inquiry-based learning not only made the subject matter more interactive and engaging but also prepared the students for real-world problem-solving in which served as a basis for STEM careers. Allowing the students to explore and investigate independently, the teachers can help them develop a growth mindset in where curiosity and the process of learning were valued.

Strategies, Programs, Initiatives, and Integration of STEM Career Promotion

Promoting STEM careers among students required the implementation of effective strategies, programs, and initiatives that integrated STEM career awareness within the educational framework. These Strategies focused on the students to provide real-world exposure, promoting the hands-on learning, and enhancing their interest in the STEM fields. Project-based learning, inquiry-based methods, and co-curricular activities are some of the key strategies used to make the STEM education more interactive and engaging in part of students. At the same time, career orientation programs, mentorship, and career fairs are important for widening the understanding of students among the various STEM career paths available to them. Project-based learning in the STEM enhanced the engagement of students and connected the lessons to the real-world context (Dacumos, 2023). The role of interactive science exhibits in increasing students' interest in STEM careers (Lubrica et al. 2021).

The emerged themes from the strategies, programs, initiatives, and integration of STEM career promotion are identified the main theme as Role Modelling and Career Exposure with four subthemes the Teacher as a Role Model in STEM Career Formation, Peer Mentoring and Student-led Support, Career Awareness through Exposure Activities, and Community and School-based Support for STEM Opportunities.

Role Modeling and Career Exposure

This theme reflected the Science Teachers' lived experiences in shaping the students' STEM aspirations through their own example and through exposure with the people related to STEM, activities, and opportunities. The Science Teachers described how they shared their personal journeys, facilitated peer support, invited alumni or professionals and connecting the lessons to real careers that helped students see the STEM as attainable and relevant career. The second theme had four subthemes the Teacher as a role model in STEM career formation, peer mentoring and student-led support, career awareness through exposure activities, and community and school-based support for STEM opportunities. Camilon (2023), which stated that STEM career choices of the students were strongly influenced by the role models, meaningful access to the learning experiences, and co-curricular activities participation and it also agreed with Lopez et al. (2022) and Berry et al. (2022), which emphasized mentoring, peer networks, research opportunities, and support systems as effective initiatives in STEM promotion.

One of the participants shared that:

"I also share stories of real STEM professionals and my own experiences as a science teacher to help students imagine themselves succeeding in these fields." (ST7)

They shared stories of real STEM professionals and their own experiences as science teachers to help the students visualize themselves in the field of STEM. They also inspired the students to make the STEM careers feel attainable by showing the students the concrete examples of success.

"I integrate STEM career orientation into my regular science lessons by consistently connecting each topic to real-world applications and the professions behind them." (ST7)

They integrated the STEM career orientation in their regular science lessons by consistently connecting each topic to the real-world applications and professions that were related to STEM. This main theme had four subthemes the Teachers as a Role Model in STEM Career Formation, Peer Mentoring and Student-led Support, Career Awareness through Exposure Activities, and Community and School-based Support for STEM opportunities.

Teacher as a Role Model in STEM Career Formation

Teachers were seen in the community as a role model by their students. The teachers' actions, words, and commitment to their work had an impact on how the students perceived not just for subjects but also the potential careers they wanted to pursue. The Teachers influenced the students by sharing their personal experiences, showing their passion towards STEM, and encouraging the students to see themselves in the same role. According to the participants they mentioned the importance of talking openly about STEM pathways and sharing diverse stories from the scientists. However, other participants highlighted that they actively promoted STEM careers by sharing their personal experiences at the same time explaining how the STEM pathways opened many opportunities both personally and professionally aspects. By stating their journeys to the students it opened for the possibilities and benefits in pursuing STEM career and it symbolized the real-life example of success in STEM field.

One of the participants described that:

"I make it a point to talk openly about STEM pathways, especially with students who may not initially see themselves in these fields. Sharing stories of scientists from diverse backgrounds, inviting guest speakers (videos from youtube) and discussing my own journey in science." (ST1)

They emphasized that science teacher proactive approach to the career awareness and motivation that addressed the students who did not recognized their potential to succeed in STEM fields by sharing the diverse stories of scientists, invite the guest speakers and offer personal reflection. The teacher helped to clarify STEM careers and make them more relatable and accessible.

"I also serve as a mentor and role model by sharing my own experiences in science research, professional development, and continuous learning." (ST5)

Three (3) out of eight (8) participants mentioned that science teachers served as mentor and role model to the students by their inspiring them with their own experiences towards STEM careers and participants engaged in training for professional growth.

"I always make it a point to share my own journey as a science teacher how choosing a STEM path opened many opportunities for me and allowed me to grow both personally and professionally." (ST7)

The science teachers as role model to shaped the perception of students in STEM career such as sharing their personal experiences and passion for STEM that the teacher inspired the students to visualized themselves in STEM fields. The teacher who shared their personal STEM journeys promotes the stronger engagement in science as the students view these teachers as real life examples of the success in the field of STEM (Gevera, 2025).

The teachers encouraged to share their own STEM journey or experiences and integrate those career stories into their lessons. Giving the students with the diverse range of role models and personalized mentorship can help them overcome the challenges in promoting STEM career. The schools and educational programs recognized the value of teachers as role models and it supports them in building connections with STEM professionals to inspire and motivate the students towards the STEM related careers.

Peer Mentoring and Student-Led Support

The Science Teachers used peer influence as another meaningful tool in career exposure. The peer in their journey can acted like their mentors and guides because it is offering support, advice, and encouragement. The peer-to-peer mentorship was impactful because they were the same age and making them easier to relate with. This kind of influenced can help among the students to feel more confident and empowered because they explored and encountered similar challenges. Berry et al. (2022) highlighted mentorship and peer networks as important forms of STEM support and engagement and Perez et al. (2021), which showed that peer support encouraged persistence in STEM despite challenges.

One of the participant mentioned that:

"I established peer mentoring that is the peer older STE learners with younger students to support networks and reinforce knowledge, hands-on, and experiential learning." (ST6)

They emphasized the use of peer mentoring as a strategy to motivate the students to explore and engage in the field of STEM. Also, peer interaction and engagement is important in developing the students STEM skills and the students can learn from one another and gain practical advice from their peers. This is huge help to the students to encourage to pursue their interest in STEM careers with confidence.

"Through the activities and projects implemented by these student-led organizations, members and leaders were exposed/get to experience the real-life applications of science, thus, encouraging them members & pursue STEM careers." (ST2)

They described that student-led organizations provided the members and leader to engage in opportunities in real-life applications of various activities and projects related to science. This hands-on exposure helped encourage the students to the value of practicality in STEM and motivated them to pursue career in STEM.

The peer mentoring should actively promoted in the STEM programs to provide an authentic career exposure and build confidence among the students. The student-led organizations and peer mentorship programs can create strong supports systems that can help the students to navigate and explore the challenges STEM and career exploration.

Career Awareness through Exposure Activities

The career exposure was important for helping the students for them to understand what STEM careers are involved and how to pursue it. By career fairs, seminars, guest speakers, and field trip the students heard the firsthand experience from the professionals in the field of STEM about their job, the challenges they faced, and what skills being required. These experiences from the Science Teachers and professional helped to bridge the gap between classroom learning and real-world reality. Blotnicky et al. (2018), which found that orientation seminars explaining specific job roles were more effective for STEM recruitment than tutoring alone.

One of the participants shared that:

"Another school-based activity that we implemented is the career seminar where we invited alumni of the STE and STEM program, who are now engineers, doctors, or data scientists to speak to the class." (ST5)

They emphasized that the importance of career seminars in providing students with direct exposure to professional in STEM fields such as inviting alumni that succeeded in STEM careers like engineers, doctors, and data scientists, so that, teachers must create opportunities for students to experience tangible examples on how STEM education translate into real-world success.

"I usually connect lessons to everyday life and real-world issues. I show them how science and Math are used in jobs that affect their communities. Career awareness activities such as career talks, guest speaker sessions, and classroom career integration days" (ST1)

Four (4) out of eight (8) participants said that the career seminars and career activities can help the students to fully understand the relevance of STEM and its potential career pathways they can pursue.

"We organized a Science Fun Day, an interactive exhibit where all students were invited to engage in hands-on activities guided by their teachers, sparking curiosity and excitement about scientific concepts." (ST3)

They emphasized that science fun day students must engage to rise their curiosity and enthusiasm for STEM, by organizing interactive exhibits and hands-on activities then the science teachers facilitated a fun and immersive learning experiences in which not only sparked excitement however it encouraged active participation in exploring scientific concepts. Learning is impactful if actively involved the students and can relate concepts to real-world experiences. The Interactive science exhibits can enhance students' interest in STEM careers (Lubrica et al., 2021).

Community and School-based Support for STEM Opportunities

STEM career promotion was strengthened when students were supported not only by their teachers but also by the school environment and the wider community that surrounded them. The community role models such as science teachers, local engineers, scientists and healthcare professionals had deep impact to the students in understanding the STEM career. Jones and Emenike (2024) highlighted the value of mentoring, community, and validation of rural identity in sustaining STEM persistence.

One of the participant described that:

"I explain to my students that STEM careers are among the best paths to take because they are highly in demand, not only abroad but also here in the Philippines, and even in our own province of Masbate. I often guide them through real examples, such as local engineers, technicians, nurses, IT specialists, and science educators who have built stable and meaningful careers through STEM." (ST7)

They highlighted that STEM careers are in-demand abroad and in the Philippines such as engineers, technicians, and nurses who built stable careers in the community. The science teacher demonstrated the stability and impacts for choosing STEM careers and helps students to see the tangible benefits of STEM by encouraging them to consider these fields as rewarding options in their future.

"One of the initiatives I have participated in to promote STEM careers is being a member of the EUREKA project, which aims to strengthen STEM learning in our school." (ST7)

Joining project helped to promote STEM career among the students within their school and they also organize clubs and organizations that enlightened students and actively participated in solving community problems. Culturally familiar and alignment in community STEM activities can improved the attitudes of rural students toward STEM (Sung et al., 2025).

"We organize science club and YES-O (Youth for Environment in school Org.). These clubs/student organizations empower and give opportunities to science enthusiasts to actively participate in solving or mitigating problems in the community." (ST2)

The science clubs and YES-O provided the students a platform to show the students passion for science and environmental issues into meaningful actions. These organizations strengthened the students through direct involving in community initiatives that allowed them to address local challenges and contribute to solve problems. This hands-on activity not only promoted an understanding of STEM fields however it encouraged the students to become proactive and responsible citizens to commit a positive impact in their community.

Reinforcing STEM career promotion within the rural communities required approaches that were beyond classroom teaching. Engaging the community as the role models and mentors enhanced the connection of students to STEM careers and provided them the real-world examples of success. Involving the students in local problem-solving activities by these initiatives cultivated a sense of empowerment and responsibility in STEM fields.

Challenges Encountered in Promoting STEM Careers

Promotion for STEM careers among students in rural secondary schools in Masbate posed set of challenges that hindered the realization of STEM potential impacts. The challenges were rooted in many factors, including the limited resources and awareness of what the STEM careers were all about, lack of sufficient resources and opportunities to expose the student in STEM field, the influence of the peers and family on the students choices is also matters, and personal barriers and motivations that molded and motivated the attitudes of students towards STEM. With these challenges it significantly impacted on the students' ability to fully engage and aspire into STEM professions. Science teaching involved content difficulty, the student readiness issues, and the need for new strategies for engagement (Geverola et al., 2022).

The emerged theme was classified as Academic Preparedness Issues and Limited STEM Knowledge with four subthemes the Limited Awareness or Knowledge of STEM Careers, Lack of Resources or Opportunities, Peer and Family Influences, and Personal Barriers and Motivation.

Academic Preparedness Issues and Limited STEM Knowledge

Academic Preparedness was essential factor in molding the students to success in STEM education. Meanwhile, the students faced significant challenges because of the limited exposure to fundamental STEM concepts in which affected their ability to process and understand the complex topics. This lack of preparedness was not only impacted their academic performance but also decreased their interests in pursuing STEM careers. Limited STEM knowledge can be rooted to many factors such as inadequate resources and outdated teaching methods that made STEM subjects feel relevant without a strong grasp of foundation knowledge the students struggled to engage with advanced topics in STEM that leads to lower level of confidence. Limited training, limited resources, inadequate facilities, and budget constraints were major barriers to effective STEM implementation (Ismail et al., 2019).

One of the participants shared that:

"The major challenge that i have encountered in promoting STEM career interest is the learners lack of readiness for the competencies set for the Phil Iri result, many of our learners are not grade level ready. Most learners lack the mastery of fundamental skills necessary to learn their current lesson." (ST2)

They encountered challenges in promoting STEM career interests due to the lack of readiness among the students for the competencies set by Phil Iri results. It indicated that many students were not grade level ready and most of them were lacked mastery in fundamental skills necessary to effectively engage with current lessons.

"I encountered many issues and concerns regarding this since that parents and stakeholders has a negative thought about STE and STEM because this is new to them and very difficult because they are not came from schools who offered special science elementary school (SSES)." (ST6)

Participant encountered issues and concerns regarding to the STEM promotions as parents and stakeholders held negative perspectives about STEM field. This was due to the facts that STEM were new

concepts for them and many of them did not come from schools that offered special science elementary school.

The academic preparedness was essential for the success of students in STEM. This gap in preparedness not only affects the student's academic performance however reduced their interests in pursuing the STEM field. The negative perspectives could further complicate the promotion of STEM careers and their unfamiliarity with STEM contributed to their resistance of it. This main theme had four subthemes the Limited Awareness or Knowledge of STEM Careers, Lack of Resources or Opportunities, Peer and Family Influences, and Personal Barriers and Motivation.

Limited Awareness or Knowledge of STEM Careers

This challenge highlighted the emotional and cognitive aspects of the students that they feel unaware of the diversity of STEM careers. A lot of students had limited to STEM career related exposure, and they only recognized the well-known fields in STEM careers. Students struggled in limited exposure, social, and geographical isolation, and difficulty transitioning to urban postsecondary settings, made mentorship and targeted institutional interventions or solution are significant for retention of the students in rural condition (Adam et al., 2024).

One of the participants emphasized that:

"Limited exposure to STEM career. A lot of students only know a few common professions, and they rarely see examples of scientists, technologists who look like them. STEM careers can feel unrealistic." (ST1)

Based on the participants, limited knowledge can make STEM careers feel unrealistic for many students and they perceived that STEM subjects are too challenging that led to many students dislike the STEM.

"One of the challenges I have encountered in promoting STEM career interest among my students is the limited exposure they have to real STEM opportunities, especially in a rural setting like ours. Many students are unaware of the wide range of STEM careers available and struggle to relate these paths to their daily lives." (ST7)

The lack of exposure to real-world STEM careers was another challenge that many students struggled to connect to what they've learned in the classroom to the practical applications of these STEM subjects in the workplace because lack of exposure created a disconnect among the students between academic learning and real-world opportunities that the STEM can offer.

"Major challenge is students limited exposure to STEM careers especially those beyond commonly known professions such as doctors, nurses, and engineers. Many students are unaware of the wide range of STEM-related careers, particularly those linked to research, technology, and emerging scientific fields. This limits their ability to fully envision diverse STEM career pathways." (ST5)

The students with limited exposure to the wider aspects of STEM careers particularly those beyond the well-known professions such as the doctors, nurses, and engineers. Many students are not informed about the diversity of career opportunities within STEM especially to those that linked to research, technology, and emerging scientific fields. It is important to introduce students to a wider range of STEM professions through career exploration activities.

Lack of Resources or Opportunities

This challenge in promoting STEM careers was lack of resources such as financial matters, physical or infrastructure, without enough facilities, equipment, or access to high-quality learning materials the science teachers were unable to provide for the students with necessary exposure to the students like hands-on activities and related to career experiences. These studies highlighted in which all identified limited facilities, inadequate budget, insufficient training, and narrow support as major STEM implementation barriers (Ismail et al., 2019; Ferrell et al., 2024; Tijap et al., 2022).

One of the participants described that:

"Limited resources sometimes mean I cannot provide as many hands-on activities as I would like, which affects the depth of their exposure to real-world STEM applications." (ST3)

They emphasized that lack of resources often prevents teachers from conducting meaningful STEM activities like laboratory experiments and field trips. This challenge pushes the science teachers to be creative and resourceful however it limits the depth of the students in exposure to real-world application for STEM.

"One of the main challenges I have encountered is students' lack of confidence and the belief that STEM subjects are too difficult or not meant for them. Limited access to resources, time, and exposure to real-world STEM experiences can also make it challenging to sustain their interest." (ST4)

Six (6) out of eight (8) participants mentioned that some of the students are lack of confidence to take this STEM pathways because it isn't meant for them and negative thought leads to negative thinking because they are less expose in STEM aspects.

"Resources constrain is also one of the factors in promoting STEM." (ST5)

The resource constraints were factors that limited the STEM promotion and suggested that school may lacked the necessary tools, materials, and funding to teach and engage the student effectively in STEM subjects. Without adequate resources like modern equipment and quality teaching materials the students may struggled to grasp the STEM concepts and experience hands-on learning that was essential in this field. Bucar (2024), whose study showed that lack of training, resources, and time constraints affected career guidance delivery.

To effectively and efficiently promote the STEM careers that there were critical needs to address the resources gaps in education. The schools prioritized the investments in modern equipment, teaching materials, and adequate training for the teachers for hands-on learning and real-world STEM experiences. With access to these resources was important in helping the students to connect academic content with career opportunities to build confidence in pursuing STEM fields.

Peer and Family Influences

These barriers to STEM engagement can be further understood that the rural is characterized by tight-knit community structures, strong family interdependence, and limited exposure to diverse career pathways compared to the highly urbanized settings. The family expectations often carry weight for shaping the students educational and career decisions because many families are engaged in agriculture, fishing, and livelihoods where their economic contribution is valued over long-term academic or professional pursuits. Since, many students share similar socio-economic status and if STEM careers are not commonly represented within the immediate social environment the students are less likely to view them as attainable or relevant compared to the urban setting where peer networks are more heterogenous because of the media exposure, industry professionals, and academic institutions which broadens the awareness of the students. This challenge highlighted deeply the influences of peer and family is essential factors in students for career decisions. Many students were heavily influenced by their family members, friends, and peers about their career choice because expectations and community exposure. These influences could either encourage the students to pursue STEM careers that depends on the attitudes, expectations, and support systems which are present within their immediate social circles. The family member was the role model that often shaped the early perceptions of the students in academic success and career potential. Same with the peers could impact the sense of belonging among the students in certain academic fields especially when it comes to challenging STEM subjects where pressure and lack of encouragement can influence the student's decision to engage or not. Peer support and parental STEM-related influences in sustaining STEM persistence (Perez et al., 2021).

One of the participant said that:

"The family and community also greatly influences the learners career choice in the future. I hope that the community will also help in motivating the young members of the community to develop interest in STEM-related careers by opening scholarship grants or giving cash incentives to board passers to encourage the younger generations." (ST2)

They emphasized that the family and community had a great impact on the student's decision making for career choices whether to discouraged or encouraged in choosing STEM pathways. That the communities could supported the interest of students in STEM careers by offering incentives such as scholarship and financial rewards for academic achievements thereby motivating the younger generation to pursue STEM related opportunities.

"I encountered many issues and concerns regarding this since that parents and stakeholders has a negative thought about STE and STEM because this is new to them." (ST6)

The challenges faced in introducing the STEM to the parents and stakeholders they were unfamiliar with these fields, their negative perception towards STEM was lack of understanding in which can created barriers to support the STEM initiatives. The need for better communication and awareness to shift these perspectives and gain broader supports for the STEM education.

"Students' career intentions are heavily influenced by their families' attitudes toward STEM education." (ST7)

They emphasized that career aspirations among the students particularly the STEM field were strongly shaped and molded by their own families' perspectives and value STEM education. The support and encouragement of families played an important role in promoting or hindering interest of students in pursuing STEM career. The final academic and career decisions were strongly influenced by personal interest, family input, and financial considerations (Ilagan, 2021).

To effectively promote the STEM career interest among the student it was important that both the families and communities were in the process. The families needed to be educated about the value of STEM education and how their support can shape the academic and career decisions of their children. The communities as well should be considered by providing scholarships and financial supports to motivate the students to pursue STEM opportunities. There was also a need to improve awareness and communication efforts to eliminate the negative perspectives about STEM in areas where it is not yet well understood. Strong role of community and social environment in the rural STEM persistence (Cain et al., 2024).

Personal Barriers and Motivations

This challenge emphasized how the personal barriers prevented the students from pursuing the STEM career. These barriers included such as low self-confidence, lack of interests and fear of failure related to the STEM subjects. Motivation, curiosity, and personal goals were additional factors that influenced the students to pursue the STEM career because some students who believed that STEM subjects were too difficult and not aligned to their interests that students less likely to pursue these STEM fields. Active learning could boost intrinsic motivation (Canning et al., 2024).

One of the participant mentioned that:

"Many students who were initially unsure or hesitant about STEM are now exploring STEM-related careers more seriously. For example, one student who struggled with confidence in math became excited about coding after participating in a robotics club and is now considering computer science as a career." (ST7)

The participant emphasized that some students expressed doubt about their ability in science however overtime engaging in hands-on projects and experimental activities changed their behavior to more curious and increased confidence in science. This showed that personal motivation and encouragement from the science teachers could help to overcome the fear, self-doubt, and low interest of the students towards STEM subjects. Engaging and interactive learning environments could help reduce fear and increase confidence to the students (Rahman, 2024).

"Some students would openly say 'I'm not good at science' over time, after engaging in experiments, projects & discussions that connected (real-life) science to real life. Many of these students began to show more curiosity and confidence!" (ST1)

Another participant shared her experience encountered in promoting STEM career among the students.

"Many students who were initially unsure or hesitant about STEM are now exploring STEM-related careers more seriously. For example, one student who struggled with confidence in math became excited about coding after participating in a robotics club and is now considering computer science as a career." (ST7)

They emphasized that the transformation in attitudes of students toward science when they are exposed to hands-on learning experiences and some students expressed their doubt in their abilities stating that they were not good at science. However, through engaging in practical experiments, projects, and discussions that connected scientific concepts to real-life situation then these students began to develop a greater sense of curiosity.

The personal barriers like low self-confidence and fear of failure required creating more interactive and engaging experiences in STEM learning. Promoting the environment where students can directly apply scientific concepts to real-world situation that science teachers can help students overcome self-doubt and develop curiosity. Additionally, motivating the students to set their personal goals and encouraging them to pursue career that aligned to their interests may support their journey into STEM.

Efforts of Science Teachers in Students Career Interests

Science teachers played an important role in molding the career interest among the students especially in the field of STEM. The science teacher was not only responsible for content delivery however they inspired and motivated the students to explore and pursue the STEM careers. Given the growing demand skilled professionals in STEM field the efforts of science teachers to spark the interest in STEM were very important and creating the learning environments more engaging that offers application of scientific concepts and providing guidance then the science teacher helped the students to overcome barriers such as lack of confidence or fear of failure. Teacher' advocacy and efforts to create inclusive learning environments broadened students' perceptions of who can belong in STEM, which aligned with the participants' focus on building self-confidence (Simons et al., 2025).

The emerged themes from the efforts of science teachers in students career interests among the rural high school students are classified the main theme as Building Confidence and Encourage Curiosity with two

subthemes the Teacher Support and positive Reinforcement, and Autonomy and Choice in Learning Activities.

Building Confidence and Encourage Curiosity

The Science Teachers played an important role in promoting confidence and curiosity among the students through supports, positive reinforcement, and creating conducive learning environment among students. This theme, building confidence and encouraging curiosity was central in promoting STEM careers especially in rural secondary schools. For the students to engage with STEM subject and pursue STEM careers they had believe in themselves in their abilities and be motivated to explore this STEM field. These strategies employed by Science Teachers to promote autonomy and choice in learning activities were equally important to encourage the students to take ownership for their learning processes and journeys. Self-efficacy or confidence in one's abilities was the strongest predictor of success in STEM fields and career choices (Popa et al., 2017).

One of the participants point out that:

"I create a classroom environment where questions are welcomed and mistakes are valued as part of learning." (ST1)

They create classroom environments that questions were welcomed and the mistakes were valued as part of their learning process. Building the confidence of the students allowed them to engage with things without fear of judgement. When the students felt their inquiries and errors were respected and encouraged them to take risk in their learning.

"Watching their confidence grow as they realized that their ideas and innovations truly mattered." (ST3)

They observed that confidence of students grow as they realized that their ideas truly mattered and the moment of recognition helped students see the value of their contribution. As the student's confidence increased they became more engaged and motivated then understanding that their work had a meaningful impact which encouraged their interest in STEM related activities. This main theme had two subthemes the Teacher Support and Positive Reinforcement and Autonomy and Choice in Learning Activities.

Teacher Support and Positive Reinforcement

The Science Teachers' positive reinforcement such as encouragement, praise, and validation can directly impacted the confidence of the students in STEM. Science Teachers can helped the students to overcome their doubt especially students expressed their negativity about their capacities and positive reinforcement helped the students to realize the success was not limited to few students, but it can be achievable with efforts, persistence, and curiosity. Supportive learning environments can improved students' attitudes towards STEM subjects (Sung et al., 2025).

One of the participant highlighted that:

"Sometimes it's as simple as encouraging a student who did well on a project. Those small moments of affirmation can spark confidence and interest." (ST1)

Another participant shared his experiences as teacher for positive reinforcement.

"Verbal encouragement is also effective in supporting students' interests. These efforts influence students positively because they become interested in some way and at the same time engage well in the class." (ST8)

They described that emphasizing the essential of small moments of affirmation had huge impact on the student's part, it helped to spark their confidence and interest in science subjects to engage more deeply in STEM. By simple encouragement like acknowledging the success of students on their projects then teachers created affirmation that motivated the students to believe in their abilities and it sparked the curiosity of the students to explore the STEM field.

"By connecting lessons to real-world applications and exposing them to STEM opportunities and career paths, I've noticed students showing greater interest in exploring STEM both inside and outside the classroom." (ST4)

They emphasized the powerful impact of the teacher support and positive reinforcement that increased the engagement of students with STEM. This connection not only enhanced the understanding of students in the subjects however motivated them to explore STEM both inside and outside the classroom.

The science teacher had an important role in shaping the attitude and interest of the students towards STEM through positive reinforcement and supportive encouragement. The simple action like acknowledging and verbal praise have significantly enhanced the confidence and motivation of the students and helping them overcome self-doubt and see the value of their efforts. The school needed invest in professional development for the teachers to emphasize the importance of positive reinforcement in ensuring that students felt supported and empowered to engage with the STEM fields.

Autonomy and Choice in Learning Activities

Providing students with the autonomy to explore STEM concepts on their own that promoted engagement, curiosity, and critical thinking. If the students had their freedom to choose, they likely engage more with the content that interested them and they are more motivated and invested in their learning. The autonomy great helped to the students to build problem-solving skills, encourage critical thinking and allows the students to explore in their own personal interest. Inquiry-based learning increased student engagement and made STEM subjects more interactive (Rahman, 2024).

One of the participant mentioned that:

"I let students experiment, test and observe rather than just listen. I create a classroom environment where questions are welcomed and mistakes are valued as part of learning." (ST1)

They emphasized that the students must encouraged to experiment, test hypotheses, and observe results for them to explore the concepts and formulate their own questions over receiving information and also inculcated the value of mistake as part of their learning process.

"Students work in research teams, simulating how scientists and engineers collaborate in real settings." (ST5)

Students were immersed in a collaborative environment that they replicated the practices of professionals like scientists and engineers. This learning experience provided the students with the opportunity and privilege to engage in real-world problem solving through working together in the team like professionals in STEM fields.

"By connecting science topics to a job, setting practical activities into a real-world job, and creating reflection from the lesson." (ST6)

Students were given the chance to connect what they learn to real-world jobs then were provided with the freedom to explore their knowledge to be applied in practical context and they actively chose how to engage with material and relate it to their own interest in the future career.

Promoting the student autonomy in STEM significantly increased the student's engagement as they felt more connected. However, when the students were encouraged to experiment and collaborate then they developed critical thinking skills, problem solving skills, and teamwork which were high valued in the real-world career. By choosing their own topics and activities that aligned with their interests that lead to deeper and more meaningful learning experience.

Ethical Considerations

This study was consistent with the ethical standards to protect the identity of the participants. An informed consent form was provided by the researcher to all participants indicating that their participation was voluntary, responses were confidential, and they could withdraw at any time without penalty. The researcher formally requested to conduct this study from the Schools Division Superintendent of the Department of Education, Masbate Province Division, as the participants were the Science Teachers of public high schools in the 2nd district of Masbate.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, the researcher concluded that science teachers played an important role in promoting STEM career interests among rural high school students in Masbate. Therefore, the science teachers in Masbate emphasized the experiential learning and focused on hands-on learning and practical exposure that helped the students connect theoretical concepts to real-world applications making the STEM careers feel more attainable. The used of inquiry-based approaches enhanced the students critical thinking and curiosity. This contributes to rural education by showing that experiential and inquiry-based learning are not only instructional strategies but also important mechanisms for the reducing the perceived distance between the rural students and STEM career opportunities. Therefore, the significant role of role modeling and career exposure in promoting STEM careers among the students and science teachers played central role in shaping the STEM aspirations of the students through sharing the science teachers' personal experiences. Science teachers efforts in role modeling, peer mentoring, and student-led support promoted the environment that encouraged students to pursue STEM field. This expanded the understanding of rural STEM education by emphasizing that science teachers function not only as content facilitators while also as career models, mentors, and cultural bridges who help the students to imagine themselves as the future STEM professionals. Therefore, the challenges were significantly impacted the engagement and interest among the students in STEM field. The academic preparedness issues and limited STEM knowledge were essential hindering the ability of students to fully engaged in STEM field. Furthermore, the limited awareness of STEM careers meant that many students were unaware, lack of resources such as the facilities and materials, peer and family support that shaped the career choices that influenced decision of the students. Lastly, the personal barriers such as fear of failure, low self-confidence, and lack of motivation that affected the

students' decisions to pursue STEM careers. This contributed to the rural STEM education by showing that challenges to STEM participation are multidimensional and interconnected that involves in academic, materials, social, emotional, and motivational factors. Therefore, it emphasized the efforts of science teachers in promoting STEM career interests among the students in Masbate. Science teachers played a key role in building the confidence and encourage curiosity among the students which were important in promoting STEM engagement. Through the consistent support and positive reinforcement of science teachers it enhanced the students' motivation towards STEM. Additionally, the autonomy and providing the students with choices in their learning activities boosted their curiosity and engagement. This contributed in the advances and understanding of rural STEM education by demonstrating that science teacher support and student independence are central to the developing the motivation and engagement in STEM among the students.

Recommendations

The recommendations of this study are grounded in the findings and conclusions derived from the lived experiences of Science teachers in promoting STEM career interests among rural high school students in Masbate. These recommendations aim to address the identified strengths, challenges, and contextual needs, particularly in relation to instructional practices, institutional support, career exposure, and community engagement. First, Science teachers in rural high schools are encouraged to continuously strengthen the implementation of hands-on, inquiry-based, and contextualized teaching strategies, including laboratory-based activities, community-oriented science tasks, and problem-solving approaches, to sustain student engagement and enhance the relevance of STEM learning. Second, school heads and administrators should provide stronger institutional support by allocating adequate resources for laboratory materials, improving science learning facilities, organizing regular STEM-related exposure activities, and supporting continuous professional development for teachers in STEM instruction. Third, the Department of Education is urged to design and reinforce programs tailored to rural contexts, such as improving access to functional science laboratories, fostering partnerships with universities and industries, and providing digital learning tools to enhance STEM education delivery. Fourth, policymakers should prioritize the development and implementation of comprehensive policies and initiatives, including STEM scholarship programs, to support and expand STEM education opportunities in rural areas, particularly in Masbate. Finally, future researchers are encouraged to conduct similar studies across diverse rural and urban settings to validate, extend, and compare the findings, thereby contributing to a broader understanding of effective strategies for promoting STEM career interests.

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